

NOTES

Metal Chelates with *bis*-2(imino)-4-Thiazolidinone

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Manuscript received 3 December 1979, revised 27 May 1980,
accepted 9 September 1980

THE preparation of metal chelates with N, N'-di(thiocarbamoyl) hydrazine has been reported by us earlier¹. *Bis*-2(imino)-4-thiazolidinone (H_2 -BITZ) which is a derivative of N, N'-di(thiocarbamoyl) hydrazine has been synthesized by adopting the literature method². In order to get structurally important chelates and also to study their antifungal activity attempts were made to synthesize metal chelates with H_2 BITZ.

Experimental

Bis-2(imino)-4-thiazolidinone (H_2 BITZ) was prepared by a known method², m.p. 260° (literature value 260°). Metal chelates prepared in the present investigation are similar to those as reported earlier². Elemental analyses of these chelates were done according to standard procedures⁴. The magnetic, electronic and i. r. spectral measurements of the chelates were carried out as described previously².

Results and Discussion

The ligand can be structurally represented in two different ways as shown in Figs. I and II.

All the complexes isolated with divalent metal ions occur as inner complex salts with metal to ligand ratio 1 : 1. In other words, the ligand loses two protons during complex formation. This behaviour along with i.r. spectral data lead us to believe that the ligand predominantly occurs in the structural form II rather than I.

The series of strong bands which are observed in the spectra of N,N'-di(thiocarbamoyl) hydrazine¹ in the region 3300 cm^{-1} and attributed to NH_2 stretching vibrations strikingly disappear in the newly synthesized ligand. The significant features of the spectra of the ligand in this range are the appearance of two to three bands at a relatively lower frequency region 3200-2800 cm^{-1} possessing the characteristic features of methylene group⁵ partially overlapped with N-H stretching vibration particularly on the higher frequency band, i.e., 3200 cm^{-1} . There is no evidence of any S-H band in the region 2600-2400 cm^{-1} .

In the region 1750-1600 cm^{-1} of the ligand spectrum there appeared two strong bands, one at about 1720 cm^{-1} and another ~1600 cm^{-1} . These bands most probably arise respectively due to C=O and C=N (acyclic) stretching vibrations⁶⁻⁸ of structure II. The C=O band of the ligand practically remains unaffected in the metal complexes⁹. On the other hand, C=N stretch undergoes a shift towards lower frequency region due to coordination with metal ions in almost all the metal complexes.

Other important vibrational bands in the ligand and the metal complexes are observed near 1350, 1240, 1200, 1140 and 900 cm^{-1} respectively. These bands do not seem to be much affected on coordination. Another band at 800 cm^{-1} which most probably arises due to C-S stretching vibration remains almost unperturbed in the metal complexes, implying that the S atom of the ring does not participate in coordination with the metal ions. Logically these observations lead us to suggest that the most probable structure of the metal complexes are as shown in Fig. III.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF *bis*-2(IMINO)-4-THIAZOLIDINONE AND ITS METAL CHRELATES

Sl. No.	Formula	Colour	μ_{eff} in B.M. at $26^\circ \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	Metal% Found (Calcd.)	Sulphur% Found (Calcd.)	Nitrogen% Found (Calcd.)
	(H ₂ BITZ)	White			27.58 (27.60)	24.03 (24.34)
2.	Cu(BITZ)	Green	1.72	21.65 (21.79)	21.86 (21.96)	21.86 (19.22)
3.	Ni(BITZ)	Green	3.28	20.38 (20.46)	22.35 (22.32)	19.25 (19.53)
4.	Co(BITZ)	Chocolate	3.80	20.50 (20.52)	22.28 (22.30)	19.07 (19.53)
5.	Fe(BITZ), 3H ₂ O	Chocolate	3.54	16.32 (16.54)	18.78 (18.94)	16.28 (16.58)
6.	Mn(BITZ)	Light-green	5.50	19.38 (19.41)	22.55 (22.62)	19.48 (19.80)
7.	Pd(BITZ), 3H ₂ O	Brick-red	Diamagnetic	27.22 (27.39)	16.50 (16.47)	14.60 (14.42)
8.	Zn(BITZ)	White		22.21 (22.29)	21.45 (21.81)	18.78 (19.08)
9.	Cd(BITZ)	White		32.98 (33.01)	18.73 (18.80)	16.32 (16.45)
10.	Hg(BITZ)	Light-yellow		46.75 (46.80)	14.85 (14.94)	13.25 (13.07)
11.	Mg(BITZ), 4H ₂ O	White		9.03 (9.42)	19.45 (19.78)	16.98 (17.27)

The bands in the electronic spectra of the ligand $\sim 46,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $45,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $40,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $37,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be either due to $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ or $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions.

The Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Mn(II) complexes are paramagnetic (Table 1) whereas the Pd(II) complex is diamagnetic. The visible absorption bands of the copper(II) complex at $\sim 14,000$ and $20,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $(^3A_{1g} \approx ^3B_{2g}) \rightarrow ^3E_g$ and $^3B_{2g}$ transitions. The charge-transfer band appears $\sim 25,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The spectrum of Ni(II) complex shows three ligand field bands at $15,500$, $20,000$ and $26,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The first band corresponds to $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(F)$ while the last to $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively.

The electronic spectra of cobalt(II) complex show a band system in the region $16,000$ to $19,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which possesses the characteristic features of the electronic spectra of known octahedral complexes. The band may be assigned to $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition in an approximately octahedral field. The observed magnetic moment of the complex (3.80 B.M.) is lower than the value expected for spin-free complex. This may be due to two types of ions, i.e., spin-free and spin-paired cobalt(II) ions. Nandi and Ghosh¹⁰ have reported several cobalt(II) complexes which possess low magnetic moments, i.e., 3.75 to 3.92 B.M. However, no definite explanation can be given here. The chelates probably possess polymeric structure wherein the ligand acts in a bi-bifunctional manner spanning towards two metal ions in *trans* positions and giving rise to the chromophore MN_4 . The octahedral field may be due to intermolecular out of plane coordination.

Acknowledgement

Grateful thanks are due to Sambalpur University and C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the Junior Research Fellowship awarded to (T.D.M.) and (H.P.M.) respectively.

References

1. K. C. SATPATHY and T. D. MAHANA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 1173.
2. P. N. DHAL, T. E. ACHARY and A. NAYAK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 753.
3. K. C. SATPATHY, H. P. MISHRA and T. D. MAHANA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 248.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", The English Language Book Society and Longman, 3rd Ed., 1969, p. 462.
5. J. R. DYER, "Applications of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", 3rd. Ed., Prentice/Hall of India, Private Limited, New Delhi, 1974.
6. K. SWAMINATHAN and H. IRWING, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 1291.
7. A. YAMAGUCHI, R. B. PENLAND, S. MIZUSHIMA, T. J. LANE, C. CURRAN and J. V. QUAGLIANO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 527.
8. R. W. OLIFF, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 2036.
9. V. V. SAVANT, J. GOPALAKRISHNAN and C. C. PATIL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 748.
10. N. N. GHOSH and M. M. NANDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 139.